

Synthesis of (+)-Dictyoprolene through (Z)-3-Nonenol, A Pheromonal Component of *Anastrepha ludens*

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Synthesis of (±)-dictyoprolene has been achieved through the transformation of (Z)-3-nonenol, a pheromonal component of female fruit flies (*Anastrepha ludens*) via three steps.

THE brown algae belonging to the genus *Dictyopteria* are known to possess a characteristic odor¹⁻³. Yamada and co-workers⁴ isolated (±)-dictyoprolene, the acetate of undec-1-en-3-ol, the postulated biosynthetic precursor of various C₁₁ hydrocarbons and the related compounds. Literature⁵⁻⁷ records few synthetic strategy for 5. We wish to report an unambiguous synthesis of (±)-dictyoprolene (5) utilising (Z)-3-nonen-1-ol (2), a male produced pheromone which elicited behavioral response from virgin female Mexican flies (*Anastrepha ludens*)⁸ and the spectral values were found to be inconsistent with the one reported in literature⁴.

3-Butyn-1-ol on reaction with 1-bromopentane in the presence of lithium in liquid ammonia⁹ afforded 3-nonyn-1-ol (1) which by catalytic hydrogenation using Lindlar's catalyst in presence of two drops of quinoline in dry hexane afforded (Z)-3-nonen-1-ol (2). The alcohol (2) was oxidised with pyridinium chlorochromate¹⁰ in presence of sodium acetate in dry CH₂Cl₂ to give the aldehyde (3) which on Grignard reaction with vinylmagnesium bromide in dry tetrahydrofuran afforded the alcohol (4) which was conventionally acetylated to the required pheromone (5) in good yield.

Experimental

Unless otherwise stated, all organic extracts were dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Purity of all analytical samples were checked by tlc. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer and 90 MHz ¹H nmr spectra on a Varian

EM-390 instrument using TMS as an internal standard. All reactions of air and water sensitive materials were performed under inert conditions (N₂).

3-Nonyn-1-ol (1) : To a freshly prepared suspension of lithium amide (prepared from 1.2 g, 0.17 mol of lithium) in liquid ammonia (500 ml) was added 3-butyn-1-ol (4 g, 0.057 mol) over a period of 15 min, stirred for another 1.5 h, then a solution of 1-bromopentane (7 g, 0.046 mol) in dry tetrahydrofuran (15 ml) was added dropwise and further stirred for 3 h. The reaction mixture was quenched with ammonium chloride, ammonia evaporated and the residue extracted with ether. Ethereal layer was washed with brine, dried, the solvent removed and the crude material was purified by column chromatography to afford 1 (4.88 g, 61%) (Found : C, 77.09 ; H, 11.31. C₉H₁₈O requires : C, 77.14 ; H, 11.42%) ; ν_{max} (neat) 3360 (OH), 2210 and 2190 cm⁻¹ (C=C) ; δ (CCl₄) 0.9 (3H, distorted t, CH₃), 1.2-1.5 (6H, m, 3×CH₂), 2.2-2.4 (4H, m, H-2 and H-5) and 4.0 (3H, t, CH₂OH).

(Z)-3-Nonen-1-ol (2) : Compound 1 (4.5 g, 0.032 mol) was hydrogenated in the presence of Lindlar's catalyst (850 mg) in dry hexane and quinoline (2 drops). When one equivalent of hydrogen was taken up, the catalyst was filtered off and the filtrate was successively washed with dilute acetic acid, aqueous sodium bicarbonate, water and dried. It was purified through chromatography (silica gel) to afford 2 (4 g, 87%) (Found : C, 75.99 ; H, 12.56. C₉H₁₈O requires : C, 76.05 ; H, 12.67%) ; ν_{max} (neat) 3380 (OH) and 720 cm⁻¹ (Z double bond) ; δ (CCl₄) 0.91 (3H, distorted t, CH₃), 1.2-1.5 (6H, s, 3×CH₂), 2-2.3 (4H, m, H-2 and H-5), 3.5 (2H, t, J 6Hz, CH₂OH), 4.1 (1H, bs, OH exchangeable with D₂O) and 5.4-5.6 (2H, m, olefinic).

(Z)-3-Nonenal (3) : To a stirred suspension of pyridinium chlorochromate (10 g, 0.03 mol) in dry dichloromethane (150 ml) was added a solution of the alcohol 2 (4 g, 0.03 mol) in dichloromethane (5 ml) at 0°. After stirring for 4 h the reaction mixture was worked up in usual manner to afford

3 (2 g, 50.7%) (Found : C, 77.10 ; H, 11.39. $C_9H_{16}O$ requires : C, 77.14 ; H, 11.42%) ; ν_{max} (neat) 1 720 (C=O) and 720 cm^{-1} (Z double bond) ; δ (CCl_4) 0.9 (3H, distorted t, CH_3), 1.3–1.5 (6H, m, $3 \times CH_2$), 2.2–2.3 (2H, m, H-5), 3.3–3.5 (2H, m, H-2), 5.5–5.6 (2H, m, olefinic) and 9.1 (1H, s, CHO).

Undeca-1,5(Z)-dien-3-ol (4) : A solution of vinyl bromide (1.5 g, 0.014 mol) was added to magnesium turnings (0.35 g, 0.014 mol) in dry tetrahydrofuran (10 ml) over a period of 15 min at room temperature under N_2 atmosphere and was stirred for 2 h. To the above cooled reaction mixture, the aldehyde (**3**) ; 2 g, 0.015 mol) in dry tetrahydrofuran (5 ml) was added dropwise and stirred for 6 h at room temperature and then refluxed for 2 h. Usual work up of the reaction mixture with saturated solution of ammonium chloride followed by extraction with ether afforded **4**. The ethereal extract was dried, solvent removed and the residue was chromatographed to get pure **4** (1.7 g, 70.6 %) (Found : C, 78.55 ; H, 11.92. $C_{11}H_{20}O$ requires : C, 78.7 ; H, 11.90%) ; ν_{max} (neat) 3 350 (OH), 1 045, 910 and 720 cm^{-1} (Z double bond) ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 0.92 (3H, distorted t, CH_3), 1.5–1.8 (6H, m, $3 \times CH_2$), 2.1–2.3 (2H, m, H-7), 2.7–3.0 (2H, m, H-4), 3.9 (1H, bs), 5.0–5.6 (6H, m, olefinic protons).

($\pm$)-Dictyoprolene (5) : A solution of **4** (1 g, 0.006 mol) in acetic anhydride (1.2 ml) and pyridine (0.5 ml) was stirred at room temperature during 12 h, poured into ice-cold water and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with cold dilute HCl, saturated $NaHCO_3$ solution, brine and

dried. After the evaporation of solvent, the residue was chromatographed over silica gel to furnish pure **5** (0.88 g, 70%) (Found : C, 74.20 ; H, 10.52. $C_{13}H_{22}O_2$ requires : C, 74.24 ; H, 10.54%) ; ν_{max} (neat) 1 740 (C=O), 1 230, 1 030, 910 and 720 cm^{-1} (Z double bond) ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 0.9 (3H, distorted t, CH_3), 1.2–1.5 (6H, m, $3 \times CH_2$), 2.01 (3H, s, $OCOCH_3$), 2.05–2.45 (4H, m, H-4 and H-7), 4.9–5.7 (5H, m, olefinic protons, and 1H, H-3).

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